

Use of *Achyranthes aspera* leaf powder (AALP) for the adsorption of methylene blue : Kinetic, isotherms and thermodynamic studies

Puja Rai, Vandani Rawat and Mahesh Chandra Chattopadhyaya*

Environmental Chemistry Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : pujaraievs@gmail.com, mcc46@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received online 06 January 2013, revised 11 January 2013, accepted 15 January 2013

Abstract : In the present study, the *Achyranthes aspera* leaf powder (AALP) was used as an adsorbent for the removal of methylene blue (MB) from aqueous solution. Batch experiments such as contact time, initial concentration, pH, dosage and temperature were studied to investigate adsorption process. The characterization of adsorbent was analyzed by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). In order to understand the surface of the adsorbent in detail, the zero point charge pH_{zpc} of adsorbent was analyzed. Adsorption isotherms were studied by Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms. Langmuir isotherms were better fit for the adsorption process. Adsorption data were analyzed using kinetic models, pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order model. Adsorption kinetics was followed by pseudo-second order model. The maximum adsorption capacity of AALP was found to be 37.03 mg/g estimated from Langmuir isotherms. Thermodynamic parameters such as Gibbs free energy ΔG° , enthalpy ΔH° and entropy ΔS° were determined.

Keywords : Methylene blue, *Achyranthes aspera* leaf powder, adsorption isotherms, kinetics, thermodynamics.

Introduction

Dyes are widely used in textile, leather, food, paper and plastics industries. The effluents from these industries containing large amount of dye is toxic to aquatic life. Dyes affect the light penetration and reduce the photosynthetic action¹. Dyes increases COD and BOD levels of aquatic body. The small amount of dye present in effluent is highly visible and undesirable². Many of these dyes are toxic and even carcinogenic which causes a serious hazard to aquatic living organism³.

Methylene blue (MB) is a basic dye, widely used to colour cottons, wools, silk, leather and paper. MB can cause breathing problem and produces a burning sensation during ingestion and may cause nausea, sweating, cyanosis, jaundice, shock and methemoglobinemia⁴. Many physio-chemical techniques have been used for the removal of dyes from wastewater such as coagulation, flocculation, ozonation, reverse osmosis and photocatalytic degradation. However, these techniques are not used due to their high cost and economic disadvantage. In contrast, an adsorption technique is considered the most versatile and widely used⁵. Adsorption technique has found

to be an economical and effective treatment for the removal of dyes from wastewater. Several lowcost adsorbents used for the removal of dye from wastewater include rice husk⁶, Indian rosewood saw dust⁷, peat⁸, oil palm trunk fiber⁹, grape fruit peel¹⁰, garlic peel¹¹, coffee bean¹², coconut husk¹³, coir pith¹⁴, wheat straw¹⁵, pine cone powder¹⁶, cotton stalk¹⁷. In the present study lowcost adsorbent *Achyranthes aspera* leaf powder (AALP) has been used for removal of MB from aqueous solution. *Achyranthes aspera* is an agriculture waste weed belonging to the family of Amaranthaceae. *Achyranthes aspera* is a discarded agriculture waste weed which is a locally available and naturally abundant. This paper reports the potential of *Achyranthes aspera* as an adsorbent for removal of MB.

Results and discussion

Characterization of the adsorbents :

The FTIR technique is an important tool for identifying functional groups in adsorbent, which are capable of adsorbing dyes. The FTIR spectra were shown in Fig. 2. The broad adsorption peaks around 3400 cm^{-1} indicates

Fig. 1. FTIR spectrum of AALP.

the presence of -OH groups, -NH groups. The peak at 2927 and 2854 cm^{-1} was assigned to C-H stretching of the methyl groups. The peak at 1245 cm^{-1} indicated the presence of phenolic groups. The peak around 1156 cm^{-1} indicated C-N bending vibration. The peak around 800-897 indicated the C-H bending vibration. The peak at 777 cm^{-1} indicated C-Cl groups.

Effect of contact time and initial concentration :

In order to investigate the optimum contact time for MB adsorption on to AALP is shown in Fig. 2. The rate of adsorption of MB increases with time and attains constant time when the equilibrium was established. The rate of removal of MB rapid at initial this is so because the availability of large number of surface area of the adsorbent for the adsorption of MB. The adsorption rate gradually decreases with time until it reaches equilibrium. This decline is due to decrease in total adsorbent surface area and less available binding sites¹⁸. The optimum time was found to be 60 min, which was used for further experiments. The amount of dye adsorbed was not changed after optimum time.

In order to investigate the effect of initial concentra-

tion on adsorption behavior of MB by using three concentrations 15, 30, 45 mg/L agitated with appropriate amount of adsorbents at constant temperature (Fig. 2). We found that the adsorption of MB increases with increasing initial concentration but gradually decreases until the equilibrium is reached, whereas the percentage removal of MB decreases with increasing initial concentration. Initial concentration provides the driving force to overcome the resistance to the mass transfer of MB between liquid and solid phase. The increasing initial concentration of MB enhances the interaction between MB and AALP.

Effect of adsorbent dose :

Adsorbent dose is an important parameter to investigate the effect of adsorbent dose on the adsorption of dye using different dose of adsorbent. The experiment was carried out by taking adsorbent doses ranging from 0.05 to 0.25 g/L with initial concentration of MB dye as 15 mg/L, without changing the volume of dye solution (50 ml) at constant temperature. It can be seen that the percentage removal of dye increased with increase adsorbent dose from 0.05 to 0.25 g/L (Fig. 3). This is so because,

Fig. 2. Effect of contact time and initial concentration on adsorption.

Fig. 3. Effect of adsorbent dose on the removal of MB onto AALP.

the greater availability of the exchangeable sites or surface area at higher concentration of the adsorbent¹⁹.

Effect of pH :

The pH is an important factor that affects the adsorption of dye on to adsorbents. The effect of pH on adsorption of MB was studied by varying pH from 2 to 12 which shown in Fig. 4. The percentage removal of dye increases with increasing pH. At lower pH adsorption of

dye is low which is due to the H⁺ ions competing with cation groups on the MB for adsorption sites.

At higher pH, the adsorption of dye is higher because surface charge density decreases with an increasing pH, electrostatic repulsion between the positively charged MB and the surface of AALP is lowered. From above results, higher percentage removal was occurred at pH 10. The uncertainty in the pH value was ±0.01.

Fig. 4. Effect of pH on adsorption of MB on AALP.

The pH_{zpc} of any adsorbent determines the pH at which the adsorbent surface has net electrical neutrality²⁰. A series of solutions were prepared in which the concentration of KNO_3 was fixed at 0.1 M and the pH of these solution were varied from 2 to 12 by adding 0.1 M NaOH or 0.1 M HCl, after the adjustment of pH 0.1 g/L adsorbent was added to 50 ml of 0.1 M KNO_3 solution in 250 ml of conical flask and agitated with the help of orbital shaker for 2 h. A graph was plotted between the initial and final pH ($\text{pH}_i - \text{pH}_f$) against the initial pH (pH_i). If the pH is greater than pH_{zpc} , the adsorbent surface negatively charged and favors uptake of basic dye to increased electrostatic force of attraction. If the pH is smaller than pH_{zpc} , the surface becomes positively charged, cations were repelled and equilibrium uptake of dye was low. The pH_{zpc} value of AALP was found to be 7.8. Thus MB adsorption of AALP is favored at higher pH than pH_{zpc} .

Adsorption isotherms :

Adsorption isotherms represent the useful data in order to investigate the mechanism of adsorption process and also describe how an adsorbate molecule interacts with an adsorbent surface. Langmuir, Freundlich isotherms model were tested with experimental data.

Langmuir isotherms :

The Langmuir isotherms is useful for identifying monolayer adsorption onto a solid surface with a finite number of adsorption sites, these adsorption sites is covered with

sorbate, no further adsorption occurs at this site. The adsorption sites are of equivalent energy. The Langmuir model is represented as²¹ :

$$Q_e = bq_{\text{max}}C_e/1 + bC_e \quad (1)$$

The linearized form of eq. (1) can be expressed as :

$$C_e/q_e = 1/bq_{\text{max}} + C_e/q_{\text{max}} \quad (2)$$

where q_e (mg/g) is the amount of the dye adsorbed per unit mass of adsorbent, C_e is the dye equilibrium concentration (mg/L) in solution at equilibrium, q_{max} is the monolayer adsorption capacity (mg/g) and b is the Langmuir constant related to the energy of adsorption. The values of q_{max} and b were calculated from the slopes ($1/q_{\text{max}}$) and intercepts ($1/bq_{\text{max}}$) of the linear plots of C_e/q_e vs C_e (Fig. 5) and are given in Table 1.

The essential characteristics of the Langmuir isotherm can be expressed by means of R_L a dimensionless constant, called separation factor or equilibrium parameters. R_L can be calculated from the following equation²².

$$R_L = 1/1 + bC_0 \quad (3)$$

where C_0 is the initial concentration of sorbate and b is the Langmuir constant. There are four possibilities of R_L value :

($0 < R_L < 1$) favorable adsorption, ($R_L > 1$) unfavorable adsorption, ($R_L = 1$) linear adsorption, $R = 0$ irreversible adsorption.

Freundlich isotherms :

The Freundlich isotherm is used for the heterogeneous

Fig. 5. Langmuir plot for the removal of MB onto AALP.

Table 1. Isotherm parameter for adsorption of MB on AALP						
Q_{max}	Langmuir			Freundlich		
	B	R_L	R^2	K_F	n	R^2
37.03	0.149	0.118	0.998	5.08	1.44	0.991

where K_f is a constant related to adsorption capacity (mg/g) and $1/n$ (mg/L) is adsorption capacity of adsorbents.

The Freundlich isotherm in linear form is :

$$\ln q_e = \ln k_f + (1/n) \ln C_e \quad (5)$$

surfaces which have different adsorption energies. The isotherm can be expressed by the following equation²⁹ :

$$Q_e = K_f C_e^{1/n} \quad (4)$$

The value of k_f and n were calculated from the intercepts ($\ln k_f$) and slopes ($1/n$) of linear plots of $\ln q_e$ vs $\ln C_e$ (Fig. 6). If value of n is greater than 1 then adsorption condition is favorable.

Fig. 6. Freundlich plot for the removal of MB on AALP.

By comparing correlation coefficient values of Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms model it can be observed that Langmuir isotherms was better fit than Freundlich. Because correlation coefficient of Langmuir is greater than Freundlich isotherms. From the above discussion it can be concluded that surface of AALP have homogenous active sites. Comparison of adsorption capacity of MB on different adsorbent was shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Comparison of adsorption capacity of methylene blue by different adsorbents

Adsorbent	Capacity (mg/g)	Refs.
Peanut hull	68.03	23
<i>Paspalum notatum</i>	31	24
Banana peel	20.8	25
Orange peel	18.6	25
Neem leaf powder	8.8	26
<i>Posidonia oceanica</i> (L) fibers	5.56	27
Cashew nut shell	5.311	28
<i>Achyranthes aspera</i> leaf powder	37.03	Present study

Adsorption kinetics :

In order to investigate the kinetics of sorbate on to adsorbent by using pseudo-first order, pseudo-second order kinetics models.

Pseudo-first order kinetic model :

The pseudo-first order model is generally applicable over the initial stage of an adsorption process. The model can be written as³⁰ :

$$dq/dt = k_1 (q_e - q_t) \tag{6}$$

The linear form of model is as follows :

$$\ln (q_e - q_t) = \ln q_e - k_1 t \tag{7}$$

where q_e and q_t are the amounts of the dye adsorbed at equilibrium and at time t (mg/g), respectively and k_1 is rate constant of adsorption. The values of k_1 and q_e were calculated from slopes and intercepts of linear plot of $\ln (q_e - q_t)$ vs t (Fig. not shown).

Pseudo-second order kinetic model :

The pseudo-second order kinetic model³¹ can be written as :

$$dq_1/dt = k_2 (q_e - q_t)^2 \tag{8}$$

Integrating equation for the boundary condition $t = 0$ to

$t = t$ and $q_t = 0$ to $q_t = q_t$, gives :

$$1/(q_e - q_t) = 1/q_e + k_2 t \tag{9}$$

which is the integrated rate law for pseudo-second order reaction. The linear form of eq. (9) as :

$$t/q_t = 1/k_2 q_e^2 + t/q_e \tag{10}$$

where k_2 is the rate constant of adsorption (g/mg/min), q_e and q_t are the amount of dye adsorbed at equilibrium and at time t (mg/g), respectively. The values of k_2 and q_e were calculated from the intercepts ($1/k_2 q_e^2$) and slopes ($1/q_e$) of the linear plots of t/q_t vs t (Fig. 7) and are reported in Table 3.

From Table 3 we found that the pseudo-first order was not fit to describe the kinetic data because the correlation coefficients value (R^2) were relatively low and the experimental values q_e did not agree with the calculated values. The correlation coefficients for pseudo-second order were relatively high, indicates the experimental values agreed with the calculated values. The pseudo-second order kinetic model is adequate to describe.

Thermodynamics :

Thermodynamic studies were performed in order to understand the effect of temperature on the adsorption of MB on AALP carried out by different temperature at 30, 40, 50 °C, and parameters such as Gibbs free energy ΔG° , enthalpy ΔH° and entropy ΔS° were calculated using the following equations :

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K_d \tag{11}$$

where R is the universal gas constant (8.14 J/mol K) and T is the absolute temperature (K) and K_d is the distribution coefficient.

The K_d value were calculated using the following equation :

$$K_d = q_e/C_e \tag{12}$$

where q_e (mg/L) and C_e (mg/L) are the equilibrium concentration of dye adsorbed on to AALP and remained in the solution, respectively.

The enthalpy ΔH° and entropy ΔS° were calculated from the following equation :

$$\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ \tag{13}$$

The equation can be written as :

$$\ln K_d = \Delta S^\circ/R - \Delta H^\circ/RT \tag{14}$$

Fig. 7. Pseudo-second order kinetics model for adsorption of MB on AALP.

Table 3. Kinetics for adsorption of MB on AALP

Initial concentration (mg ⁻¹)	$q_{e,exp}$ (mg g ⁻¹)	Pseudo-first order			Pseudo-second order		
		K_1	$q_{e, cal}$	R^2	K_2	$q_{e,cal}$	R^2
15 mg/L	6.73	0.018	1.17	0.956	0.251	6.62	0.999
30 mg/L	13.17	0.015	1.37	0.861	0.169	12.98	1.00
45 mg/L	18.85	0.058	10.71	0.970	0.020	20.40	0.999

ΔH° and ΔS° were calculated from the slope and intercept from the plot of $\ln K_d$ and $1/T$, respectively (Fig. 8).

The negative value of ΔG° indicates the feasibility and spontaneous nature of adsorption process. The negative value of ΔH° indicates the exothermic nature of the process. The negative value of ΔS° shows decrease in degree of freedom of the adsorbed species. From this figure it can be concluded that the rate of adsorption capacity decrease with increasing temperature. The value of ΔG° , ΔH° , ΔS° was shown in Table 4.

Materials and method :

Preparation of adsorbent :

Achyranthes aspera leaves were collected from the University campus. They were first washed thoroughly with double distilled water to remove color components, dust, dirt and other impurities. The leaves were firstly

dried at room temperature and then in hot air oven at 70–80 °C.

The dried leaves were ground to a fine powder and sieved to obtain a 0.25 mesh size and stored in an airtight container for further use.

Adsorbate solution :

Methylene blue dye (MW = 319.86, λ_{max} (nm) = 665, solubility in water = 40 g/L (20 C°), color index number 52015) supplied by Central Drug House (P.) Ltd., India was used as an adsorbate. A stock solution (1000 mg/L) of MB was prepared by dissolving an appropriate amount of dye in double distilled water.

Instrumentation :

The pH was maintained using Digital pH meter (Systronics 335). The pH was calibrated by buffer 7.01, 4.01 and 9.00 (± 0.02) solutions and supplied by Merck.

Fig. 8. Effect of temperature on adsorption of MB onto AALP (adsorbent dose = 0.1 g, particle size = 0.25 mm, pH = 10).

Table 4. Thermodynamic parameter of free energy (ΔG°), entropy (ΔS°) and enthalpy (ΔH°)

Temperature (°C)	ΔG° (kJ/mol)	ΔH° (kJ/mol)	ΔS° (J/mol K)
30	-5345.51		
40	-5521.71	-6.65	-17.62
50	-5697.91		

Concentration of dyes was obtained using UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Systronics 2202). FTIR spectra were obtained using FTIR (ABB FTLA 2000). Orbital shaker (Shivam ISO 900/2000) was used for shaking of solution. Solution was centrifuged using centrifuge machine (Remi R-8C BL).

Batch equilibrium studies :

The adsorption experiments were carried out in a batch process using stock solution of MB. Stock solution of MB was diluted to desired concentration of 15–45 mg/L. All experiments were performed by adding a 0.1 g of AALP to a 50 ml of dye solution taken in a 250 ml conical flask. The pH was adjusted using 0.1 M HCl and 0.1 M NaOH solution with the help of Digital pH meter. Conical flasks containing solution were shaken with the help of orbital shaker for desired time at constant temperature and after that solutions was centrifuged and then final concentration of dye in supernatant solution was

determined at wavelength (λ_{\max} 665 nm) using double beam UV-Visible spectrometer. The optimum equilibrium concentration and contact time were determined and found to be 15 mg/L and 60 min respectively for further studies.

The percent removal of dye obtained on AALP was calculated by following equation :

$$\% \text{ Removal} = \frac{C_0 - C_e}{C_0} \times 100 \quad (15)$$

where C_0 and C_e are the initial and final concentration (mg/L) of dye respectively.

The amount of dye adsorbed on AALP at equilibrium (mg/g), was calculated by :

$$q_e = \frac{(C_0 - C_e)V}{W} \quad (16)$$

where q_e is the quantity of dye adsorbed on the adsorbent at time of equilibrium (mg/g), C_0 and C_e are the liquid-phase concentrations of dye at initial and equilibrium respectively, V is the volume (L) of solution and W is the mass of adsorbent (g).

Conclusion

In the present study, it has been demonstrated that *Achyranthes aspera* leaf powder, low cost adsorbent and

easily available, can successfully employed for the removal of MB from aqueous solution. The point zero charges pH_{zpc} of AALP was 7.8. The adsorption of MB onto AALP is favored at higher pH 10 lower temperature 30 °C. The adsorption kinetics followed a pseudo-second order model. Langmuir isotherms model was better fit for the adsorption of MB on AALP. The maximum adsorption capacity of AALP was found to be 37.03 mg/g. The adsorption process was spontaneous and exothermic.

Acknowledgement

Thanks to University Grants Commission for fellowship and Sushmita Banerjee for their valuable help.

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